

“Active Gas” in Stirling Engines

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I’ve recently been thinking about the possibility that the working gas in Stirling engines might not always be in an entirely “normal” state. This was prompted by reading a series of research papers on the subject of “Active Nitrogen”, written by Robert Strutt (4th Baron Rayleigh) between 1911 and 1947. These papers are now freely accessible on the Royal Society website, and make fascinating reading.

His last paper, “*The surprising amount of energy which can be collected from gases after the electric discharge has passed*”, is particularly interesting, as it describes how certain “activated” gases, at low pressure, and relatively low temperature, can induce large amounts of heat in certain metals, on contact, as the gases “deactivate”. [ref 1]

Robert Strutt “activated” the nitrogen by discharging a capacitor through a few turns of wire wrapped around the outside of the glass vessel holding the low pressure test gas [see figure 1]. This process was known as “electrodeless discharge”, and was a technique developed during the late 19th century. The nitrogen inside the glass vessel would then glow, with a faint yellow colour, for some time afterwards.

Strutt discovered that if the active gas was allowed to contact particular metals, it could raise the temperature of the metal by a considerable amount. Copper seemed to work well, and he even found that the heat transferred into gold was sufficient to melt it – despite the glass vessel remaining cool enough to touch throughout.

The question of what state the gas was in, whilst activated, was the subject of much debate, as well as subsequent research by other labs. Robert Strutt was of the opinion that the effect was mostly due to diatomic nitrogen gas disassociating during electrical activation, and that the gas recombined on contact with the metal

surface, in a catalytic fashion, releasing heat into the metal. Subsequent work, by other researchers, showed that the situation was far more complex, and that the “activated” gas could also be partially ionised, as well as becoming “excited” (i.e. electrons shifting to higher energy orbits, releasing energy on subsequent “relaxation” - as happens in a gas laser). [ref 2]

Figure 1

The effects are most easily seen in low pressure gases, of various types, but some of these activation effects can be induced in higher pressure gases – albeit invisibly, and with a much shorter “time to deactivation”.

So how could this information help us in analysing, designing, and building Stirling engines?

To extract power from a gas in a closed cycle reciprocating engine, we need to induce changes in pressure and volume. Annoyingly, by using the normal kinetic gas laws and heat transfer formulae, we only seem to be able to get so far in predicting the performance of real engines. The theoretical predictions also tend to get further from actual engine performance as engine size is reduced, and speed is increased.

However, if during one part of a cycle, gas is absorbing some energy (for instance) by electron excitation during transient contact with the heater – then that energy is not immediately available to increase the kinetic gas temperature. Similarly, if the gas is giving up energy (previously stored as excitation) by heating the surfaces of the cooler, then the gas will not be able to lose as much kinetic heat as might be assumed from measuring the heat flow in the coolant. Both these processes could help to facilitate a transfer of energy from the heater to the cooler without contributing anything to the increase and decrease in kinetic gas pressure that would be desired for mechanical power production.

This might sound like bad news. It suggests that “active gas” processes could hinder the Stirling cycle, and reduce efficiency – especially for the small, relatively fast, engines that many of us focus on.

But could the process be somehow used to enhance the cycle in some way? And how might “active gas” (if present) interact with a regenerator?

One clue might be in the strange behaviour of “thermal lag” engines. There are already various hypotheses surrounding the behaviour of these peculiar devices, but maybe the possible effects of gas activation should be included in the hypothetical mix, for future experiments.

For instance, if partially “activated” gas was to somehow transfer heat energy into the wire wool of a thermal lag engine (thereby raising the temperature of the wire above that of the gas, in a

cyclical fashion), the wire might then be able to transfer energy back to the gas, during the expansion stroke, as conventional kinetic heat.

Similarly, if “gas deactivation” could be arranged to occur within a Stirling cycle regenerator matrix, it might raise the matrix temperature above that of the gas passing through. The regenerator would then function as a full secondary heater, rather than simply being an “intermediate thermal store”.

All the above is simply speculation, of course. Suitable experiments need to be devised, and carried out, to determine if there is, indeed, any mileage in pursuing “active gas” as an addition to Stirling cycle theory.

References:

[1] Robert J. Strutt (4th Baron Rayleigh). *The surprising amount of energy which can be collected from gases after the electric discharge has passed*. Proceedings of the Royal Society A. Volume 189, issue 1018. May 1947.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1947.0041>

[2] A. Nelson Wright & C.A Winkler. *Active Nitrogen*. Academic Press Inc. 1968

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